

TAKE HOME MESSAGE-BIOGEOCHEMISTRY SESSION

- Members of the Community are interested
- Low numbers of group is not a problem
- Offline coupling in general/Online for small experiments (thus also the possibility of FPS)
- Need for a protocol but not very strict (to make everything comparable)
- Next steps: mail to medcordex (with me as contact point) and creation of a channel in the medcordex channel to discuss further steps (ask the participants)